

THE IMPORTANCE OF MAPPING VILLAGE POTENTIAL AS CAPITAL VILLAGE-OWNED ENTERPRISES (BUMDES) IN EFFORT TO IMPROVE THE ECONOMY OF CUPAK VILLAGE, NGUSAKAN DISTRICT, JOMBANG REGENCY EAST JAVA PROVINCE

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Abstract

This study aims to map the potential of micro and small enterprises (SMEs) and describe the success of businesses in the mitra University 17 August 1945 Surabaya in Cupak Village, Jombang Regency. This research is a quantitative descriptive study supported by qualitative data using mixed research methods. Potential business opportunities in Cupak village today are agricultural cultivation and handicrafts. This agricultural cultivation means businesses related to agricultural production such as tubers (porang and gadung) and also the craft of woven mats from pandan leaves. Market-based agricultural business or market needs. The types of businesses mentioned above have broad market potential with clear targets. The processed food business in question is a business managed by a group or individual with local raw materials such as porang and gadung. From the results of the SMEs data collection in Cupak village, 60% of the businesses in the village have been running for more than 6 years, but only 30% of the business actors in the village have a sales turnover of more than 1 million per month. From this data, it can be seen that mapping the potential of village business capital is very important in Cupak Village.

Keywords: *capital; SMEs; village-owned enterprises*

A. Introduction

In research, capital mapping is very important for the MSME process. Capital is the most important part in the development of a business. For an MSME that is just starting out or is still on a small and medium scale, capital management is the most important thing to be able to advance their business. There are many ways that can be done to manage capital, one of which is by mapping capital. Capital mapping is a basic and important thing that must exist in an MSME. Capital mapping itself can be obtained based on data from village mapping carried out. data was collected through the full involvement of the village community in determining field findings for the mapping process. These SMEs do not want to be bothered with complicated planning and prefer flexible MSME marketing strategies. This reason is due to the limited budget for marketing, so entrepreneurs must find effective ways to market their products or services with low marketing costs or even without spending costs. This study aims to map the potential of the village in the field of capital and the second is to be able to make research activities in the field of mapping village potential. This research is expected to be useful for MSMEs so that they can be used as reference materials for MSMEs to analyze the

implementation of marketing activities in their businesses, as data assistance for MSME development and as an evaluation of MSMEs.

8 Standards in National Research

1. Research Result Standard

The first standard in research is from the aspect of research results. The results of this study are all the outputs obtained during research activities that follow established procedures and standards. It is hoped that the results of this research will be able to support the development of science and technology as well as improve the welfare of the community. All research results that do not have a negative or harmful impact should be published. The publication itself can be by means of seminars, publications, patents, and so on. In essence, all ways that can help disseminate research results so that they are easily accessible to the wider community can be used as options.

2. Research Content Standards

The second research standard is related to research content, which includes basic research and applied research. As for the content of the research is the criteria that must be met by the content of the research itself. The main focus is the breadth and depth of the research content. In basic research, research content is expected to meet the criteria as research results (outputs) in the form of explanations or findings that can solve problems. While in applied research, the research content is expected to focus on innovation or the development of science and technology. The results of the research (outputs) are then applicable or easy to apply so that they can work as expected.

3. Research Process Standard

National Research Standards also cover aspects of the research process, so that all processes or stages in research must comply with standards. The default is:

- a. Research activities consisting of planning, implementation, and reporting.
- b. Fulfill scientific principles and methods systematically in accordance with academic and cultural autonomy.
- c. Considering quality standards, work safety, health, comfort, and security for researchers, the community, and the environment.

4. Research Assessment Standards

A research activity will also be assessed for its quality, the procedure is in accordance with the rules or not, the results have met the criteria or not, and so on. Research in universities is expected to meet the assessment standards which include:

- a. The assessment is carried out in an integrated manner by fulfilling the educational,

objective, accountable, and transparent aspects.

- b. Must pay attention to content standards, results standards, and research process standards.
- c. Using research methods that are relevant, accountable, and also represent the achievement of the criteria for the research process and results.

5. Research Standard

National Standards The next research is from the aspect of researchers. So, not all lecturers can do research in a university environment. Unless the lecturer meets national standards which include:

- a. Have the ability to carry out research activities.
- b. Mastering research methods that are in accordance with the scientific field occupied by lecturer.
- c. Determine the authority to conduct research activities according to the guidelines determined by the Deputy for Research and Development Strengthening.

6. Standard of Research Facilities and Infrastructure

The next standard is related to all facilities and infrastructure of research activities. The facilities and infrastructure referred to are all facilities owned and provided by universities to support research. The facilities and infrastructure used must meet the standards, namely:

- d. Fulfill quality standards.
- e. Meet work safety standards.
- f. safety standards,
- g. comfort standard,
- h. Health standards, and also
- i. Safety standards for researchers, communities, and the surrounding environment.

7. Research Management Standard

The next standard is from the aspect of research management, where each university is expected to have a team that manages research activities. The management is expected to be the same as or close to the research governance of various research institutions in Indonesia.

The tasks of the team or work unit that are part of the management of this research are planning, implementing, controlling, monitoring and evaluating, as well as reporting research activities.

8. Funding Standards and Research Financing

The next standard is related to research funding and financing. So, there is a minimum funding limit that must be provided to support the implementation of research activities. Where this funding source can come from internal university funds, it can also come from the government

and institutions and industries that are research partners. The existence of a minimum funding limit standard helps researchers carry out research without worrying about stopping in the middle of the road because they run out of funds.

B. Methods

The measuring instrument in quantitative research is in the form of a questionnaire, the data obtained in the form of answers from Cupak villagers to the questions or items proposed. Good points are as follows:

- a. Items must be relevant or tied to what is being measured
- b. Items must be concise
- c. The details are not confusing
- d. Good points must contain one mind

This research uses linear regression analysis method because the independent variable consists of one variable. The variable that affects is called the Independent Variable (independent variable) and the variable that is affected is called the Dependent Variable (the dependent variable). SPSS Tabulation

Results

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	6.624	1,350		4.906	.000		
	X	.404	.113	.561	3.585	.001	1,000	1,000

a. Dependent Variable: Y

Model Summaryb					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.561a	.315	.290	.818	1,722
a. Predictors: (Constant), X					
b. Dependent Variable: Y					

Substituted Coefficients:

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$$Y = 6.624 + 0.404 X$$

Solution

Coefficient of determination

R² = 0.315, which means that the variation of Y is influenced by the variation of X by 40%, while the remaining 60% is influenced by other variables that are not accurate.

Coefficients Tabel Table

Regression Equation

$$Y = 6.624 + 0.404 X$$

a = 6.624 means that if X is 0, then Y = 6.624

b = 0.404 means that if X is increased assuming other variables are fixed then Y will increase by 0.404

C. Results and Discussion

1. Partner Profile Mapping

The area mapped in this study is Cupak Village, Ngusikan District, Jombang Regency. Cupak Village is located in the northern part of Ngusikan District. Cupak village is bordered by Asem Gede Village in the north, Kromong Village in the east, Made Village, Kudu District in the south and Hutan in the west. Most of the area of Cupak village is teak forest with hilly reliefs. Cupak Village consists of: Dusun Cupak and Dusun Mungut. The two hamlets are separated by forest with a distance of 6 Km and there is no adequate road access connecting the two hamlets. The potential of Cupak Village include:

1. Natural potential, has a religious tourism area of Mount Pucangan and a campground.
2. Potential yields of Porang, Corn and Gadung plantations. Their crops are sold only as raw materials, which in fact will have a much more useful potential to support the local community's economy if they are processed into processed products.
3. Small industry, there are 12 residents who produce wood charcoal but it is still done with the traditional system because it has not been touched by appropriate technology, besides that a lot of waste is generated because small fractions of charcoal production are thrown away because they are not sold.
4. Livestock, the majority of residents raise goats and cows but it is still done conventionally, so the capacity for raising livestock is very small due to the inability to provide animal feed
5. Craftsmen, the majority of residents to obtain additional results, namely the majority as craftsmen of pandan mats.

Cupak Village has potential in the field of Agriculture / plantations, including:

- a. Porang, Porang in Cupak Village have very good quality, this is proven by many porang producing areas that take seeds from Cupak Village. The planting area in Cupak Village is very large and has not been fully exploited, this is due to constraints in the marketing field during the harvest season and the appreciation of low prices for (wet) log products because porang farmers do not understand the true benefits of porang and there is no touch of technology and technology. porang processing knowledge
- b. Maize, agricultural land is very suitable for growing corn, but the problem faced by farmers is limited marketing channels, which depend on a few middlemen

Gadung, Gadung in Cupak Village grows wild and abundantly because the contours of the land are suitable for Gadung plants so that many people's gardens (gardens) grow Gadung plants. However, Gadung is sold in logs (wet) because there is no touch of technology and knowledge about gadung processing and limited market access

2. Mapping of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

Cupak Village has potential in the MSME sector, including:

- a. Wood Charcoal, the quality of wood charcoal is very good, namely the export quality of wood charcoal, but it is still carried out with the traditional

system where the sale is through one of the collector companies. In producing wood charcoal, it is still carried out using the traditional system because it has not been touched by appropriate technology, besides that a lot of waste is generated because small fractions of charcoal production are thrown away because they are not sold. This waste can be processed into wood charcoal briquettes which have high value.

- b. Pandan mats, the majority of the people of Cupak village have side income, namely making pandan mats, this can be developed as a souvenir product to support it as a tourist village, for example bags, wallets, tissue holders, etc.

3. Farm Mapping

The residents of Cupak Village on average raise cows and goats, this is strongly supported by the abundance of animal feed sources, namely forage feed and agricultural waste, but the farming system is still conventional, namely by looking for feed every day in the teak forest, as well as in the fields or gardens every day, so the capacity livestock is very limited because the ability to provide feed is limited.

4. Institutional Mapping

Cupak Village already has institutions to support village progress, including: 1) BUMDES (Village Owned Enterprises); 2) KOPWAN (Women's Cooperative); 3) POKDARWIS (Tourism Awareness Group). However, the existing institutions have not been able to run properly. From research activities in Cupak Village, data obtained from village business actors in Cupak are as follows:

No	Name	Business Name	Address	Gender	Age	Business Period	Factors That Develop Business
1	Suwandi	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT 01/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	40-49 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
2	Supriyanto	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
3	Suja'i	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing

No	Name	Business Name	Address	Gender	Age	Business Period	Factors That Develop Business
4	Pardi	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
5	Gaguk	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	30-39 Years	3-5 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
6	Yateman	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	30-39 Years	3-5 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
7	Ahmad Pandi	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	30-39 Years	3-5 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
8	Juri	Charcoal	DSN. CUPAK, RT03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	3-5 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
9	Wakini	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
10	Winarti	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
11	Sustiani	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	6-8 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
12	Yulis	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT01/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	40-49 Years	9-11 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
13	Partini	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	40-49 Years	9-11 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
14	Saini	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	>11 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
15	Lami	Pandan Woven (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	>11 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing

No	Name	Business Name	Address	Gender	Age	Business Period	Factors That Develop Business
16	Ruwanti	Pandan Chicken (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT 03/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
17	Sumarlik	Pandan Chicken (Mat)	DSN. CUPAK, RT 03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
18	Sariatun	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	5-6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
19	Warlik	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	1-2 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
20	Suami	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	5-6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
21	Nuriati	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	1-2 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
22	Samah	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	>50 Years	1-2 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
23	Susniawati	Gadung Chips	DSN. CUPAK, RT 01/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Woman	30-39 Years	1-2 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
24	Didik M.	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	40-49 Years	5-6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
25	Ngateman	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 03/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
26	Nardi	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/01, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
27	Indro As.	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	40-49 Years	>6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing

No	Name	Business Name	Address	Gender	Age	Business Period	Factors That Develop Business
28	Sutrisno	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	40-49 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
29	Darmaji	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 02/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	>50 Years	5-6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing
30	Kasturi	Porang	DSN. CUPAK, RT 04/02, KEC. GUSKAN, JOMBANG	Man	40-49 Years	> 6 Years	Technology, Venture Capital, Marketing

D. Conclusion

Village capital mapping research is useful to find out the extent of independence and resources owned by the village. Mapping was carried out in various fields, including: village profiles, mapping of types of micro, small and medium enterprises, demographic mapping of residents, mapping of the organizational field, and mapping of the livestock sector. In addition, from the results of the UMK data collection in Cupak village, 60% of businesses in the village have been running for more than 6 years, but only 30% of business actors in the village have a sales turnover of more than 1 million per month. From these data, it can be seen that mapping the potential of village business capital is very important in Cupak Village. suggestions for future researchers are to be able to do mapping and writing in other fields and methods, such as in multiparadigm reviews.

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